

How AI can support standardization in artificial fertilization

The role artificial intelligence (AI) can play in assisted reproductive technology (ART)

Viviane Aicher
DSIA.bbM.20.WS21
FH Kufstein Tirol
Kufstein Tirol Austria
2010837035@stud.fh-kufstein.ac.at

ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence has found its way into many areas of life in recent years and can provide useful knowledge, especially in the medical field, for example in the area of cancer research. This article is intended to give data scientists an insight into the field of assisted reproductive technology (ART) for artificial fertilization and to provide an overview of the latest studies with artificial intelligence in this area. For this purpose, various websites of fertility clinics as well as the latest scientific articles on this field were screened and combined. The article does not provide a discussion of the robustness of each finding, but discusses the general limitations of the studies. It is shown that various algorithms and AI systems already exist for the various steps of artificial fertilization, but that these must be subjected to long-term verification in real clinical and laboratory everyday life.

KEYWORDS

Artificial intelligence (AI), assisted reproductive technology (ART), in-vitro fertilization (IVF), intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI), intracytoplasmic morphologically selected sperm injection (IMSI), support vector machine (SVM), convolutional neural network (CNN)

1 Introduction

Having children is the most normal thing in the world, at least until it happens that all efforts remain unsuccessful. In fact, every 10th couple in Germany is involuntarily childless. The causes of fertility disorders are manifold and can lie with both women and men. For example, a woman's low egg cell reserve or a low sperm count can lead to the disorder [1].

With the help of assisted reproductive technology (ART), there has been a therapeutic option since 1978 for a childless couple to fulfill the wish to give birth to a child. The IVF method (in-vitro fertilization) used at the time is still one of the central fertilization methods alongside the ICSI method (Intracytoplasmic Sperm Injection), which was established in 1992, as a new milestone in reproductive medicine for couples in whom the man has limited sperm quality, later improved by the IMSI method (Intracytoplasmic Morphologically Selected Sperm Injection) [2].

Over the years, the drug treatment and timing have been refined, and techniques such as assisted hatching, in which a too thick egg shell is scratched with a laser beam, have been added to increase the success rate of artificial insemination. Still, the current success rate of IVF is no more than $\sim 30\%$ and much research revolves around improving this low rate [3].

A more detailed clarification of the fertility disorder includes comprehensive individual advice with clarification of living conditions and previous illnesses as well as detailed examinations of both partners, which, depending on gender, include ultrasound, blood samples and spermograms [4]. Furthermore, a genetic diagnosis based on the blood sample, which includes the analysis of the chromosomes (cytogenetics), and a targeted analysis of individual genes (molecular genetics) can be carried out [1].

In order to understand how artificial intelligence could influence assisted reproductive technology, the procedure of ART is first explained below. Afterwards, the latest studies on artificial intelligence in connection with ART are listed and their current limitations are discussed.

2 Explanation of ART

Assisted reproductive technology is a fertility treatment that comprises several procedures such as insemination, in-vitro fertilization (IVF), intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI), intracytoplasmic morphologically selected sperm injection (IMSI), cryopreservation of gametes or embryos, and the use of fertility medication.

An Intra-uterine insemination can be offered as a first option to treat infertility and requires open fallopian tubes in women and a normal spermogram in men. With the help of follicle-stimulating hormones / gonadotropins or with clomiphene, an attempt is made to bring 1 to 2 follicles in the ovary to maturity. Ovulation is then initiated by means of the human Chorionic Gonadotropin (hCG) hormone and the prepared semen is introduced into the uterine cavity. Certain hormones (e.g. progesterone) have to be taken in some cases up to the 12th week of pregnancy [2].

If this first option is not suitable other procedures - as described above - can be taken. Those procedures have common stages in the ART cycle and are listed in timely sequence in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Common ART cycle

2.1 Hormone stimulation

The woman injects herself subcutaneously with the individually determined dose of the follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) for about ten to twelve days, depending on the growth of the follicles so that several follicles form in the ovaries. The growth of the follicles and thus the maturation of the egg cells is closely monitored by means of an ultrasound examination and monitoring of the hormone levels in the blood [5].

2.2 Egg retrieval (follicular puncture)

In order to retrieve the egg cells, the follicles are punctured with 3D ultrasound guidance to visualize the follicles. This is done transvaginally with the help of a rod-shaped transducer to which a thin puncture needle is attached. The follicular puncture is performed under brief sedation so that the patient does not feel any pain. The fluid from the follicles is removed and then examined for egg cells in the laboratory [5].

In case of previous implantation failure or repeated miscarriages due to an impaired immune response of the endometrium, intralipid infusions based on soy can be used to reduce the activity of natural killer cells (in the blood and / or uterus). For this purpose, an infusion is given both on the day of the egg collection and one day before the embryo transfer and then every 14 days until the 12th to 20th week of pregnancy [6].

2.3 Extraction of the sperm cells

At the same time as the egg retrieval, the man gives a semen sample so that sperm cells are available for fertilization [5].

2.4 Fertilization

Assessment of egg and sperm quality (e.g. degree of maturity, morphology) has to be undertaken. The mature egg cells can then be fertilized by selected spermatozoa in the laboratory using different methods: IVF, ICSI or IMSI which are further described below [2, 5].

2.4.1 In-vitro fertilization (IVF)

In-vitro fertilization (IVF) describes the union of the egg cell and sperm by themselves after being put into a reagent dish (=in vitro) [2].

2.4.2 Intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI)

Using the method of intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) the union of the egg cell and the sperm is not left by itself in the reagent dish, but a selected sperm is directly injected into the egg. The ICSI procedure can be used to help couples in situations where the spermogram results indicate limited male fertility [2].

2.4.3 Intracytoplasmic morphologically selected sperm injection (IMSI)

The intracytoplasmic morphologically selected sperm injection (IMSI) method is similar to the ICSI; however, a high-resolution microscopy is used for a better morphological assessment and selection of the spermatozoa [2].

These three methods can be supported by further special techniques such as spindle analysis, assisted hatching, hyaluronan binding test (PICSI) and polarization microscopy.

After one of these fertilization procedures are undertaken the fertilized eggs are transferred into a special culture medium and placed in an incubator in order to grow into embryos [2].

2.5 Embryo development phase

The fertilized egg - called zygote - changes very quickly in the first few days. After 24 hours, the zygote starts splitting into daughter cells so that at the fourth day there are already embryos with 16 to 32 cells. The zygote resembles a blackberry at this time, which is why this phase is also known as the berry or morula stage [7].

The blastocyst forms on the fifth day after the egg cell is fertilized with the semen. It is the first form of the embryo in which different cells can be recognized. But the blastocyst is still growing in the original egg shell, with a small cyst in the center. The different zones in the blastocyst are divided into three sub-areas: inner part (embryoblast) from which the baby will develop, outer part (trophoblast) from which the placenta will be formed and inner cavity (the fluid inside the blastocyst) which is still the subject of intense research [7].

The stage of development of the blastocyst can be graded and is of particular interest in artificial insemination because in this stage the embryo is about to implant in the uterus [7].

2.6 Embryo transfer

Once the embryos have reached a certain stage of development (blastocyst), one to a maximum of three embryos - that may be used in Germany - are selected and drawn up into a thin catheter to be subsequently placed into the woman's uterine cavity [5].

Prior to the transfer a pre-implantation diagnosis (PGD) which is a genetic examination of the embryo to determine hereditary diseases or genetic changes in the genes can be undertaken. This is carried out before implantation in the uterus with some cells that have been removed from the embryo about five days after fertilization [8].

2.7 Cryo-preservation

If during the treatment excess fertile egg cells arise, they can be frozen (cryopreservation). These so-called egg cells in the pronuclear stage can later be thawed and develop into embryos to retain a valuable chance of a new embryo transfer without new egg retrieval [5].

2.8 Aftercare

The administration of progesterone is useful to support the implantation of the embryo after the transfer and is usually done with hormone capsules that are used vaginally [5].

2.9 Pregnancy test

17 days after the egg cells have been removed, a determination of the pregnancy hormone hCG in the blood can be used to make a reliable statement about the outcome of the treatment (pregnancy test) [5].

3 Explanation of AI

Artificial intelligence (AI) can be seen as an umbrella term for Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Natural Language Processing, Reinforcement Learning and Deep Reinforcement Learning which are techniques that use different mathematical algorithms to process data without explicit programming and are capable of generating predictions based on complex pattern recognition by incorporating the processing power of computers [9, 10].

With increasing computational power, the use of artificial intelligence has gained more and more importance in medicine over the last decades and can now for example classify the severity of cancer through the use of medical images [11].

4 How AI can support ART

In the ART cycle the right treatment at the right time, the correct gamete selection and the proper embryo selection is critical for success [12]. The determination of those three aspects are highly individual and complex tasks to perform. In fact, there is a high variation in success rates likely due to the subjectivity of current assessment methods [12]. Hence a successful ART treatment could be described as an act of artistic creation by the embryologist based on his or her knowledge, experience and intuition.

In order to overcome this subjectivity several studies have been undertaken to obtain more standardized methods based on artificial intelligence algorithms. These studies vary widely concerning the type of data examined like the embryo or blastocyst images, time lapsed and cycle data, the number of samples used, the AI and ART methods used, the selected features, the desired outcome like embryo implantation, pregnancy or live birth and the reported performance [13].

Figure 2 provides an overview of the various areas of artificial intelligence studies in respect to the ART context which will be discussed in the following sections along the newest findings.

Figure 2: Overview AI areas in ART context

4.1 Treatment regimen

As stated above in ART the right treatment at the right time is essential for the success of the artificial fertilization. This also includes the right dose and timing of medicine prescribed.

4.1.1 Hormonal stimulation of the ovaries

In their study, Letterie et al. developed a computer-based system for daily monitoring of ovarian stimulation during the IVF cycle,

which includes the following 4 decisions: 1. Stop or continue stimulation. If the decision is stop, then the follow-up decision would be 2. Trigger or abort. If the decision is to continue, then the subsequent decision would be 3. The number of days to continue and 4. Whether a dosage adjustment is necessary [14].

Their predictive analytical algorithm has a high level of accuracy and has been compared with evidence-based decisions by teams of experts. The tool offers a potential platform for optimizing clinical decision-making during IVF [14].

4.2 Gamete selection

Gametes are the reproductive cells of an organism. Female gametes are called egg cells and male gametes are called sperm. Gametes are haploid cells and each cell carries only one copy of each chromosome.

4.2.1 Sperm classification

The enhanced Kruger criteria, which describe the viability of the sperm, can be used to classify the sperm. While some researchers have already been able to predict the division into their own categories with a high accuracy of over 88% in 2017 with the help of a support vector machine (SVM), Thirumalarajuet et al. applied deep transfer learning with the use of smartphone microscopy to develop a low-cost technique that can accurately measure sperm morphology using the Kruger criteria [13, 15, 16].

4.2.2 Egg cell maturity determination

To select the right egg cells at the right stage of maturity, Targosz et al. used 71 deep neural network models for semantic egg cell segmentation. They trained their algorithm to identify the following morphological characteristics of the egg cell: clear cytoplasm, diffuse cytoplasm granularity, smooth endoplasmic reticulum cluster, dark cytoplasm, vacuoles, first polar body, multipolar body, fragmented polar body, perivitelline space, zona pellucida, cumulus cells and the germinal vesicles (GV). The study achieved an accuracy of about 85% for the training pattern and 79% for the validation [17].

4.3 Embryo selection

4.3.1 Embryos in pronuclear stage embryos

To assess embryo quality and development, there are morphological features that can be used for embryos in the pronuclear stage, such as the size, shape and orientation of the pronuclei and the overall appearance of the cytoplasm [18]. Only zygotes with two different pronuclei are considered normal and suitable for transmission. In 2021, Zhao et al. used a convolutional neural network (CNN) to segment embryos in the pronuclear stage. They examined the morpho kinetic patterns of the zygote, the pronuclei, the cytoplasm and the zona pellucidae. With their model, they achieved an accuracy of 84% for the pronuclei, over 97% for the cytoplasm and approx. 80% for the pellucid zone. The authors

concluded that their CNN system can potentially feed into clinical practice for segmentation in the pronuclear stage as a tool with high precision, reproducibility and speed [19].

4.3.2 Embryos in splitting stage

Embryos are generally selected for transfer by visual inspection of the embryos based on only three characteristics: blastomeric cell number, percentage of total cytoplasmic fragmentation, and degree of asymmetry of the blastomeres [20].

Kanakasabapathy et al. used a deep learning convolutional neural network (CNN) to train and validate assessment using embryo images on day 3, based on the results of embryo development recorded on day 5 of culture. The CNN was trained to make the following day-5 developmental predictions: embryo arrest, morula, early blastocyst, full blastocyst, and high-quality blastocyst. The accuracy of the prediction of blastocyst development was 71.9% (95% CI 68.4–75.2%) [21]. To improve the accuracy of the model's predictions in identifying embryos that will eventually develop into blastocysts, embryo morphology on days 2 and 3 of development was included. The neural network then outperformed embryologists in identifying embryos that correctly developed into blastocysts ($P < 0.0001$) and the overall accuracy of the prediction ($P < 0.0001$).

Bormann et al. presented a novel Key Performance Indicator (KPI) for monitoring embryonic culture conditions at the developmental stage of cleavage. This AI-based KPI predicted the percentage of cleavage stage embryos that would develop into high quality blastocysts on day 5 of development and had the highest association with sustained pregnancy rates ($R^2 = 0.906$). This is the first AI-based split-stage KPI that has been shown to detect changes in a cultural environment that shift pregnancy outcomes [22].

Kelly et al. used a CNN to identify safe regions on a cleaved embryo to perform laser-assisted hatching. The CNN was tested on nearly 4000 cleavage images and had an accuracy of 99.4% with a 95% CI between 99.1% and 99.6% [23].

4.3.3 Static image blastocyst analysis

As the study by Fernandez et al. shows, a wide variety of AI models have been developed to determine embryo transfer [13]. Bormann et al., for example, have created a CNN model for the classification of blastocysts that are suitable for implantation on the basis of the morphological quality of the internal cell mass (ICM), the trophectoderm (TE) quality and the degree of expansion of the blastocyst with an accuracy of 90% (compared to non-blastocysts) [24].

Thirumalaraju et al. found that an Xception model – which is a deep convolutional neural network architecture developed by Google that involves depth wise separable convolutions - is very well suited to classify blastocysts based on their morphological quality and correctly classified more than 99.5% of the highest quality blastocysts that are best suited for transfer [25].

4.3.4 Time-lapse microscopy (TLM) image analysis

In order to observe and simulate cell division over several days, images can be made using time-lapse microscopy [26]. These series of images can then be processed with the help of artificial intelligence and predictions regarding the blastocyst quality and possibly even the potential of the embryos to implant can be made [27, 28, 29].

5 Current Studies and their Limitations

If one considers the different areas in which there is research on the support and standardization of assisted reproductive technology (ART) through artificial intelligence, the following picture as shown in Figure 3 emerges. It can be observed that AI already covers most of the stages of an artificial fertilization cycle.

Figure 3: Stages of ART covered by AI

To be able to use these studies in the future to relieve staff of intensive manual work as well as to get a standardization independent of subjective assessment criteria, the results of the algorithms must be tested in real clinical and laboratory everyday life and continuously supplemented with further data sets and features. That, of course, requires new validation in order not to function sub optimally through use in real life and to deliver a robust and valid result [30].

For supplying these algorithms and developed systems with as much data as possible across clinics, clinics and laboratories would have to collect the data uniformly, which is unfortunately not yet the case at the moment [31]. In addition, the collection of data is sometimes misleading, such as the question of smokers or non-smokers. The more correct question would be whether or the patient is consuming nicotine on a regular basis, since nicotine can also be absorbed through other ways than smoking. As a result, algorithms can be fed with wrong data and deliver incorrect results.

A one-sided data basis, too little data or unsuitable algorithms can also lead to prejudices in artificial intelligence. It is therefore

important to question the models at regular intervals and to re-validate them with embryologists.

6 Conclusions & Perspectives

In summary, it can be said that there is already extensive research on the extent to how and which algorithms of artificial intelligence (AI) can support assisted reproductive technology (ART) in order to simplify and standardize the currently very individual and clinic-specific treatments and thus gain more independence in the art of creation of fertilization from the knowledge, personal experience and daily constitution of the embryologist. So basically, one can say that AI can take out the art of ART.

However, these studies still have to prove themselves over the long term in everyday clinical and laboratory life and have to be further refined.

With the rapidly increasing computing capacity, it would be conceivable to undertake studies that use algorithms with unsupervised learning on the combination of the results of cytogenetics and molecular genetics of the couples in the future in order to identify possible causes of a not obvious fertility disorder and thus maybe even explain the low success rate of artificial fertilization.

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